

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D9.3 Press Kit

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Project

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Executive Summary

This deliverable introduces the press kit and promotion package. The COVINFORM press kit consists of two parts: (i) a press kit for media representatives, and (ii) a promotion package for consortium partners that provides the necessary means to promote the project in communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. These materials may be used for communication (promoting the project to the different target audiences), dissemination (raising awareness of project results), and exploitation (utilising the results), following the strategies defined for dissemination and exploitation (D9.1) and communication (D9.2). As such, they are in line with the project's communication and dissemination strategies, in particular addressing the communication objective of providing widespread visibility to the project and its outputs; and developing a project brand and messages for each stakeholder group to create visibility and interest in the project's solutions, activities and results and thus target all stakeholders.

With the progress of the research and relevant findings of the project, both the press kit as well as the promotion package will be extended and updated as needed. As such, this task will be continued, and the promotion package extended throughout the project.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
CMYK	Cyan, Magenta, Yellow, and Key (black), a colour model.
EPS	Encapsulated PostScript, a graphics file format.
PDF	Portable Document Format, a file format.
PNG	Portable Network Graphics (.png), an image file format.
RGB	Red, Green, Blue, a colour model.

1 Introduction

The COVINFORM press kit consists of two parts: (i) a press kit for media representatives, and (ii) a promotion packages for consortium partners. While the former addresses media representatives directly, the latter contains materials and tools to promote the project in communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. For the latter, partners will follow the strategies defined for dissemination and exploitation (D9.1) and communication (D9.2). In particular, the materials below are meant to address the communication objective of providing widespread visibility to the project and its outputs; and developing a project brand and messages for each stakeholder group to create visibility and interest in the project's solutions, activities and results and thus target all stakeholders.

2 Press kit

The COVINFORM press kit and its individual contents are available for download on the project website via <https://www.covinform.eu/media/>.

It contains the following materials:

- Logo
- Project summaries
- Partner introductions
- Press release(s)
- Leaflet
- Project presentation (slide kit)
- Poster/infographic

In the following, each of these materials is briefly presented.

2.1 Logo

The COVINFORM logo is provided for download in different sizes, with transparent and white background, and different colour versions (RGB for screen, CMYK for print). Different formats (eps, pdf, png) are provided, as well as clear space information and a colour sheet.

Figure 1. Logo

2.2 Project summary

Short summaries of 500 and 1.000 characters gives a concise overview of the project.

Table 1. Project summaries

500 CHARACTERS (GENERAL PUBLIC)	500 CHARACTERS (SCIENTIFIC AUDIENCE)
COVINFORM analyses COVID-19 responses on the level of government, public health, community, and information and communication with a focus on the impacts on vulnerable individuals and groups. Key outcomes of the project are an online portal and visual toolkit for stakeholders in government, public health, and civil society integrating data streams, indices and indicators, maps, models, primary research and case study findings, empirically grounded policy guidance, and creative assessment tools.	COVINFORM is drawing on intersectionality theory and complex systems analysis to analyse COVID-19 responses on the level of government, public health, community, and information and communication with a focus on the impacts on vulnerable individuals and groups. Key outcomes of the project are an online portal, a visual toolkit for governmental stakeholders, indicators, maps and models, primary research and case study findings, empirically grounded policy guidance, and creative assessment tools.
1.000 CHARACTERS	
The COVINFORM project analyses COVID-19 responses on the level of government, public health, community, and information and communication. With a focus on the intersectional nature of health and socioeconomic vulnerabilities, the interdisciplinary consortium assesses the impact of the pandemic and its repercussions on societies and vulnerable groups, as well as constructively critiques COVID-19 responses. The project will conduct research on three levels: 1) EU27 MS + UK+ Israel: analysis of secondary data and development of models; 2) 15 target countries: analysis of documentary sources on the national level; 3) 10 target communities: quantitative and qualitative empirical research. Key outcomes of the project are an online portal and visual toolkit for stakeholders in government, public health, and civil society integrating data streams, indices and indicators, maps, models, primary research and case study findings, empirically grounded policy guidance, and creative assessment tools.	

2.3 Partner introductions

Partner introductions are provided on the project website, focusing on each organisation's expertise.¹ A social media campaign is being conducted introduces each organisation's role in the project.

2.4 Press release(s)

As outlined in D9.2, COVINFORM will issue several press releases throughout the project's lifetime, whenever a noteworthy event occurs. A first press release has been issued at the project start, announcing the project and its aims²; subsequent press releases will be added.

2.5 Leaflet

A project leaflet provides a short overview of the project, as well as the project objectives, funding information, partners, and contact information. Further factsheets will be designed based on key outcomes and insights, recommendations, or for the purpose of fieldwork.

¹ Available at <https://www.covinform.eu/consortium/>

² Available at <https://www.covinform.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/39/2020/11/COVINFORM-Press-release-Project-Launch.pdf>

Figure 2. Leaflet

2.6 Project presentation (slide kit)

A slide kit introduces the project and presents its key facts, objectives, methods and intended impacts, as well as the project partners.

Figure 3. Slide kit

2.7 Poster/infographic

Finally, a project infographic/poster presents the overall project structure and its key outcomes at a glance. Complementing the factsheet, poster puts focus on the case studies and cross-cutting issues (government, public health, community, and communication), which are at the centre of the project.

Figure 4. Poster/infographic

3 Promotion package

In addition to the press kit for the media, partners are provided with a promotion package. A selection of materials is presented in the following; partially, these have been introduced in D9.2 together with the project identity. SYNYO will design new materials based on the needs of the partners, as well as depending on the different project outcomes; as such, this task will be continued, and the promotion package extended throughout the project.

The following materials are included in this non-exhaustive list:

- Templates
 - Templates for social media posts
 - Templates for brochures
 - Templates for press releases
 - Further templates for policy briefs, scientific reports, etc.
- Video call background image
- Stickers
- Rollup
- Video intro & outro
- Business cards

3.1 Templates

In addition to deliverable and presentation templates already described in D9.2, SYNYO has designed templates for social media posts in different variations and for different social media platforms (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook), as well as templates for brochures and bi-monthly reports, as well as press releases. Currently under design are templates for reports targeted at a more scientific audience. Templates for policy briefs, policy recommendations and whitepapers will be designed accordingly as soon as the first output has been created. SYNYO will also design posters and other materials for partners for conferences or other events. As such, project partners will be equipped with all relevant and necessary materials to circulate among participants of conferences, workshops, and other events and bi-lateral meetings.

Figure 5. Templates for social media posts

Figure 6. Templates for brochures

3.2 Video call background image

For the participation in webinars and similar activities, SYNYO has designed a background image.

Figure 7. Video call background image

3.3 Stickers

Stickers can be used for various promotional purposes, advertising and supporting identity building and recognisability of the project.

Figure 8. Stickers

3.4 Rollup

A rollup can be used at events and promotional purposes as an effective way of presenting the project and its identity to audiences.

Figure 9. Rollup

3.5 Video intro & outro

COVINFORM will issue several videos throughout its lifetime. As such, SYNYO has designed an intro and outro to ensure video materials are recognisable and consistent. The outro also includes all partner logos and the funding acknowledgement. Videos can be found on the projects [YouTube channel](#).

3.6 Business cards

Business cards designed according to the project identity allow partners to promote their involvement in the project.

Figure 10. Business cards

4 Conclusions

This deliverable presents the project's press kit, as well as a promotion package for partners. Submitted at month 6 of the project, it will be extended and updated as needed according to the progress of the research and relevant findings of the project. As such, this task will be continued throughout the project. For example, as attending conferences and other events in person become more realistic, goodies such as branded disinfectant will be designed.

As defined in the communication strategy (D9.2), COVINFORM follows an online-first approach, thus reducing its ecological footprint. The press kit is published on the project website³; promotion material for partners are provided in the drive. Whenever relevant, materials will be printed/produced as well.

³ Available for download via <https://www.covinform.eu/media/>